

VARIATIONS IN SEED PHYTIC AND OXALIC ACID CONTENTS AMONG NIGERIAN COWPEA ACCESSIONS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH GRAIN YIELD

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ABSTRACT

A total of 99 Nigerian cowpea landraces collected from the Genetic Resources Unit of the International Institute of Tropic Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan Nigeria, were studied for variability in seed contents of phytic acid and oxalic acid and for the relationships among the antinutrients and grain yield. Phytic acid and oxalic acid concentrations were determined using spectrophotometric and titrimetric methods respectively, while grain yield parameters were measured in a greenhouse under ambient environmental conditions. The result showed very significant variations in both the antinutrients and grain yield ($p < 0.0001$). Phytic acid values ranged from 2.58 – 3.87 with a mean of 3.10 ± 0.23 mg/g; oxalic acid varied from 0.58 - 0.97 with an average value of 0.78 ± 0.08 mg/g; seed weight per plant (SWPP) ranged from 1.50 - 11.92 with a mean value of 6.96 ± 2.97 g; pod length (PL) ranged from 11.06 - 28.10 with an average value of 16.01 ± 2.84 cm; while seed number per pod (SNPP) varied from 8.60 - 19.20 with a mean value of 13.29 ± 3.16 . The study revealed wide variations in the antinutrients and grain yield among the cowpea cultivars. Some of these variations may be genetic and may provide an opportunity for genetic development of cowpea lines with superior grain yield quality, low in the antinutrients. No significant correlations were detected among the antinutrients and any of the grain yield indices suggesting that grain yielding capacity has no influence on the seed content of phytic and oxalic acids in cowpea.

KEYWORDS: Cowpea seeds, phytate and oxalate content, grain yield.

INTRODUCTION

Antinutrients or anti-nutritional factors (ANF) are plant's secondary metabolites which act to reduce food nutrient utilization (Soetan, 2008). However, being antinutrients is not an intrinsic characteristic of a compound but depends on the metabolic processes of the ingesting animal (Akande *et al.*, 2010). For instance, Trypsin inhibitors, which are ANFs for monogastric animals, do not exert adverse effects in ruminants because they are degraded in the rumen. According to Harborne(1989), the reason for ANFs in plants seems to be as a way of storing nutrients or as a means of defense from destruction by insect pests and grazing animals. Plants contain thousand of compounds which, depending upon the situations, can have beneficial or deleterious effects on organisms consuming them. These compounds, with the exception of nutrients, are referred to as 'allelochemicals' (Conn, 1979). ANFs may be considered as a class of these compounds, which are generally not lethal. They diminish animal productivity but may also cause toxicity during periods of scarcity or confinement when food containing these compounds is consumed by animals in large quantities.

Some antinutrients have been shown to possess pharmacological values. Saponins, tannins and flavonoides, for examples, possess anticancer and cytotoxic properties (Koratkar and Rao, 1997; Das and Mahato, 1983; Schopke and Hiller, 1990; Wakabayashi *et al.*, 1997). Phytic acid's mineral binding properties is believed to prevent colon cancer by reducing oxidative stress in the lumen of the intestinal tract (Vucenik and Shamsuddin, 2003; Jenab and Thompson, 2000). The chelating effect may serve to prevent, inhibit, or even cure some cancers by depriving those cells of the minerals (especially iron) they need to reproduce (Klopfenstein *et al.*, 2002).

Antinutrients are found in almost all foods. However, their levels are reduced in most common food crops probably through selection during the process of domestication. Nevertheless, the large fraction of human diets that come from these crops raise concern about the possible effects of antinutrients on human health (Cordain, 1999). The possibility now exists to eliminate antinutrients entirely using genetic engineering, but since these compounds may also have beneficial effects, such genetic modifications could make the food crops more nutritious without the capacity to improve other aspects of human health (Welch, 2004).

Phytic and oxalic acids are among the major antinutrients present in plant protein sources (Akande *et al.* 2010), both being antiminerals. Phytic acid, also known as inositolhexakisphosphate (IP6), or phytate when in salt form) is the principal storage form of phosphorus in many plant tissues, especially bran and seeds (Klopfenstein *et al.*, 2002). It is not digestible to humans or nonruminant animals, because these animals lack the digestive enzyme (phytase) required to remove phosphate from the inositol in the phytate molecule. On the other hand, ruminants readily digest phytate because of the phytase produced by microorganisms in their rumen (Klopfenstein *et al.*, 2002). Phytate is well documented to block absorption of not only phosphorus, but also of other minerals such as calcium, magnesium, iron and zinc (Ramiel, 2010; Klopfenstein *et al.*, 2002). When a mineral binds to phytic acid, it becomes insoluble, precipitates and will be nonabsorbable in the intestines (Akande *et al.* 2010). This process can therefore contribute to mineral deficiencies in people whose diets rely on these foods for their mineral intake (Hurrell, 2003; Ramiel, 2010; Klopfenstein *et al.*, 2002). World Health Organization has recognized phytate as one of the main causes of anaemia, an iron deficiency disease (Bath, 2006). The ratio of phytic acid to minerals present in foods may serve as an indication of the availability of the minerals in question. For example, a high phytic acid to zinc molar ratio greater than 15:1 indicates low mineral availability from that food (Akande *et al.* 2010).

Phytic acid also inhibits several proteolytic enzymes and amylases (Singh and Krikorian, 1982). The presence of phytic acid and other antinutrients in the diet may therefore result in food indigestion (Bell, 1971), some portion of which may remain unabsorbed in the colon and become fermented by intestinal bacterial flora (Ramiel, 2010).

Oxalic acid and its salts (oxalates) occur as end products of metabolism in a number of plant tissues. These plants may produce adverse effects when eaten in large doses, because oxalic acid also binds calcium and other minerals making them nutritionally unavailable or forming harmful complexes. Consumption of large doses of oxalic acid has been associated with kidney stone, corrosive gastroenteritis, shock, convulsion, low plasma calcium and urinary damage, with vegetarians at higher risk, especially women who require greater amounts of calcium in their diet (Philips, 1993). However, soaking, cooking, boiling and other food processing methods generally achieve significant reduction of the antinutrients (Udensi *et al.*, 2005 and 2007; Ekop *et al.*, 2004; Ekop and Eddy, 2005b). Thus, foods high in these antinutrients should be adequately processed to make them wholesome for consumers. In ruminants however, dietary oxalic acid can be degraded by rumen microbes into CO₂ and formic acid (Allison *et al.*, 1990). The amount of antinutrients in food crops is highly variable and depends on factors including environmental condition, use of high-phosphate fertilizers in cultivation and genotypic variation (Offoret *et al.*, 2011).

In this study, the genotypic variability of phytic and oxalic acids among Nigerian cowpea cultivars and their relationship with grain yield was studied to provide a guide for choice of cowpea lines based on phytate and oxalate contents and to ascertain if grain yielding capacity of a cultivar has any influence on its contents of these antinutrients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Materials

Seeds of a total of 99 Nigerian cowpea genotypes were used. All the seeds were obtained from the Genetic Resources Unit of the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, Nigeria.

Determination of Grain yield

Grain yields of the cowpea cultivars were measured based on pod length (PL), seed number per pod (SNPP) and seed weight per plant (SWPP). The experiment was conducted in the greenhouse facility of the Biotechnology Research and Development Centre (BRDC) of the Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki in Nigeria between 15 September and 28 December 2009 under ambient environmental conditions. Plastic pots (6-L) with aeration holes at the bottom were filled with sandy-loam soil. They were watered to field capacity one day before sowing and spaced 100 x 100 cm apart on the floor of the greenhouse. Six seeds were sown in each pot and watering was done twice a week for full emergence of the seedlings. Ten days after sowing, the plants were thinned to three plants per pot. Regular watering was continued twice a week until the plants were four weeks old and they were then watered every two days as the plants transpiration increased. The plants were grown to full maturity with no addition of fertilizer or any agro-chemical and data were collected in replicates of ten for PL and SNPP and three for SWPP.

Determination of Phytic Acid and Oxalic Acid Contents

Phytic acid was determined by a combination of two methods. The extraction and precipitation of phytic acid were performed according to the method described by Wheeler and Ferrel (1971). Iron in the precipitate was measured according to the method of Makover (1970). A 4:6 Fe/P ratio was used to calculate the phytic acid content. The titration method described by Day and Underwood (1986) was used to determine the oxalic acid content of the powdered seed samples.

DATA ANALYSIS

All data were analyzed for variation by the ANOVA procedure of SAS Software version 9.1 (SAS Institute, 1998). Differences were declared statistically significant at $P < 0.05$. Where significant differences were detected, the means were separated by the Tukey's Studentized Range (HSD) Test at 5% probability level. Correlations among the variables were determined using the Pearson simple correlation procedure of the SAS software.

RESULTS

The cowpea accessions showed very high degree of variability in both phytate and oxalate contents ($p < 0.0001$). The seed phytate content of the 99 accessions ranged from 2.58 – 3.87 with an average of 3.10 ± 0.23 mg/g, while the oxalate content varied from 0.58 - 0.97 with a mean value of 0.78 ± 0.08 mg/g (Table 1).

The result clearly showed that cowpea seeds contain more phytic acid than oxalic acid. The mean phytic acid obtained in this study (3.10 mg/g) is about four times higher than that of oxalic acid (0.78 mg/g). Simple analysis of the result showed that only about 16% of the analyzed cowpea population had phytate values above the mean value and that only about 14% had phytate values below the average value, while majority of the accessions (70%) had phytate values within the mean range (3.10 ± 0.23 mg/g). Oxalate was similarly distributed among the cowpea genotypes. Only about 15% had values above the average value (0.78 ± 0.08 mg/g) and 14% had values below the average, whereas as high as 71% were within the average range.

Similarly, grain yield (measured as seed weight per plant, pod length and seed number per pod) varied widely among the accessions ($p < 0.0001$). Seed weight per plant (SWPP) ranged from 1.50 - 11.92 with a mean value of 6.96 ± 2.97 g, pod length (PL) varied from 11.06 - 28.10 with a mean value of 16.01 ± 2.84 cm, while seed number per pod (SNPP) varied from 8.60 - 19.20 with an average of 13.29 ± 3.16 seeds per plant. No significant correlation was detected between phytate or oxalate and any of the grain yield indices (Table 2).

Table 1. Mean Values of Phytic acid, Oxalic acid and Grain Yield Indices in Nigerian Cowpea Lines.

Genotype	Accession No.	Phytate (mg/g)	Oxalate (mg/g)	SWPP (g)	PL (cm)	SNPP
1	TVu-46	3.20±0.11	0.72±0.01	6.53±1.00	19.46±1.69	13.00±2.35
2	TVu-160	3.05±0.05	0.80±0.01	2.31±0.34	19.72±3.22	11.60±2.19
3	TVu-331	3.05±0.05	0.68±0.01	3.18±0.39	17.22±1.55	10.60±1.82
4	TVu-442	2.58±0.03	0.86±0.01	4.36±0.68	16.22±0.86	17.20±0.84
5	TVu-461	2.90±0.02	0.76±0.02	8.95±0.96	18.98±2.49	18.20±1.48
6	TVu-561	3.07±0.08	0.58±0.01	9.64±0.70	15.86±1.70	15.20±1.30
7	TVu-702	3.23±0.04	0.89±0.01	9.46±0.65	16.30±3.06	18.00±2.55
8	TVu-729	3.25±0.11	0.77±0.01	10.53±1.08	14.50±0.76	16.80±1.30
9	TVu-764	3.16±0.08	0.73±0.02	9.30±1.22	19.88±0.69	19.20±0.45
10	TVu-839	3.20±0.06	0.71±0.01	7.10±1.24	18.36±0.90	18.40±0.89
11	TVu-848	3.04±0.08	0.66±0.02	6.81±0.93	18.18±0.90	16.80±1.92
12	TVu-867	3.33±0.05	0.66±0.02	4.58±0.83	13.86±0.64	12.80±1.30
13	TVu-930	2.90±0.05	0.75±0.02	2.70±0.82	15.84±1.90	11.80±1.92
14	TVu-939	3.32±0.02	0.76±0.02	5.93±0.24	17.76±0.58	15.80±1.30
15	TVu-1138	3.05±0.05	0.69±0.01	4.60±0.69	19.28±0.94	12.80±2.59

Table 1.contd

16	TVu-1197	3.41±0.01	0.61±0.02	7.14±0.79	15.50±1.60	11.20±2.17
17	TVu-1260	2.94±0.10	0.80±0.00	5.78±0.57	17.38±0.20	15.80±1.30
18	TVu-1262	3.11±0.00	0.68±0.01	11.78±1.41	16.34±0.77	18.40±1.67
19	TVu-1263	3.08±0.03	0.83±0.03	4.22±0.82	14.64±1.33	14.60±1.95
20	TVu-1455	3.27±0.02	0.74±0.01	2.26±0.56	13.52±1.33	11.00±1.41
21	TVu-3910	3.31±0.01	0.74±0.04	2.96±0.50	13.60±0.93	12.00±2.55
22	TVu-3919	3.02±0.03	0.84±0.02	11.92±1.96	14.52±0.57	10.40±1.82
23	TVu-3933	2.82±0.03	0.65±0.03	5.62±0.79	13.32±0.50	14.00±1.00
24	TVu-3960	2.76±0.03	0.88±0.02	7.74±1.38	19.16±1.01	16.60±2.07
25	TVu-4007	2.97±0.02	0.78±0.02	8.32±1.35	15.28±0.75	13.20±0.84
26	TVu-4009	3.00±0.03	0.74±0.02	10.25±1.36	14.54±0.42	13.00±1.22
27	TVu-4015	3.10±0.02	0.78±0.01	10.27±1.42	18.08±0.75	16.60±1.52
28	TVu-4028	2.89±0.02	0.85±0.01	4.91±0.56	14.72±1.01	12.00±2.35
29	TVu-4034	2.85±0.02	0.79±0.03	7.21±1.41	13.16±1.47	8.60±2.30
30	TVu-4044	3.23±0.01	0.76±0.03	2.09±0.25	15.64±2.49	13.00±1.58
31	TVu-4045	2.85±0.03	0.73±0.03	1.75±0.42	19.18±1.38	14.60±1.95
32	TVu-4046	2.92±0.03	0.84±0.03	7.86±1.16	16.42±0.60	16.20±1.30
33	TVu-4047	3.11±0.05	0.92±0.03	1.50±0.75	16.00±2.50	16.40±1.67
34	TVu-4049	2.76±0.01	0.85±0.03	4.35±0.85	14.66±1.49	15.00±1.87
35	TVu-4068	2.94±0.02	0.85±0.04	8.05±1.13	12.48±1.31	10.60±2.07
36	TVu-4083	2.92±0.12	0.72±0.01	4.38±0.98	17.04±1.49	14.60±1.14
37	TVu-4089	3.03±0.07	0.65±0.03	9.84±1.35	14.92±0.55	12.80±1.92
38	TVu-4095	3.15±0.06	0.76±0.01	7.31±1.37	15.82±2.47	13.40±2.19
39	TVu-4100	3.12±0.04	0.76±0.03	9.43±1.54	14.12±1.37	12.80±2.28
40	TVu-4260	3.24±0.06	0.76±0.04	10.92±1.49	16.92±2.27	12.80±3.35
41	TVu-4408	3.23±0.09	0.90±0.02	6.23±0.87	12.82±1.07	10.60±1.34
42	TVu-4415	3.43±0.02	0.78±0.01	11.06±1.32	15.20±0.72	10.20±2.17
43	TVu-6318	2.76±0.00	0.74±0.01	10.41±1.48	16.42±1.13	11.80±2.39
44	TVu-6320	2.84±0.05	0.71±0.00	9.51±0.87	19.60±1.72	13.00±2.12
45	TVu-6325	3.00±0.04	0.78±0.02	9.76±1.39	17.70±1.10	14.40±2.19
46	TVu-6674	3.27±0.04	0.74±0.02	10.29±1.02	17.80±1.79	13.20±2.77
47	TVu-6778	3.48±0.01	0.73±0.03	7.96±0.65	11.06±0.86	11.20±2.05
48	TVu-6804	2.96±0.03	0.85±0.03	9.49±1.54	15.48±1.36	12.40±1.67
49	TVu-6815	3.17±0.03	0.78±0.03	3.69±0.16	12.46±0.99	8.60±2.41
50	TVu-6819	3.36±0.02	0.66±0.01	6.50±0.97	13.14±1.12	10.40±1.67
51	TVu-6822	3.14±0.04	0.70±0.02	9.31±0.83	13.50±0.58	11.00±1.00
52	TVu-6830	3.35±0.02	0.71±0.01	3.02±0.54	16.40±0.80	14.60±1.67
53	TVu-6833	3.40±0.05	0.67±0.01	10.63±0.80	13.30±0.55	10.80±1.64
54	TVu-6847	3.49±0.04	0.69±0.03	7.95±0.90	14.06±1.16	8.60±1.82
55	TVu-6932	3.32±0.01	0.77±0.01	4.82±1.14	28.10±3.62	13.00±2.45
56	TVu-7083	3.03±0.03	0.85±0.01	3.70±0.77	15.14±1.51	13.80±2.59
57	TVu-7097	2.73±0.02	0.73±0.01	5.62±0.69	14.52±0.54	12.40±0.89

58	TVu-7109	2.76±0.03	0.91±0.01	6.70±1.58	16.02±1.51	10.60±2.07
59	TVu-7110	3.47±0.03	0.81±0.02	10.84±0.88	13.56±1.43	8.80±1.30
60	TVu-7112	3.26±0.03	0.63±0.01	7.55±0.91	15.32±1.06	12.60±2.30
61	TVu-7117	3.87±0.03	0.94±0.01	11.88±1.78	13.66±1.91	10.40±2.70
62	TVu-7488	3.07±0.05	0.82±0.01	4.89±0.64	17.22±0.62	13.80±3.11
63	TVu-7491	2.99±0.04	0.78±0.02	6.18±1.13	15.58±0.24	9.80±0.84
64	TVu-7531	3.34±0.03	0.76±0.01	2.96±0.98	18.08±1.34	11.40±2.30
65	TVu-7815	2.87±0.08	0.71±0.02	6.06±1.24	12.88±1.04	10.20±1.92
66	TVu-7833	3.26±0.01	0.71±0.02	3.17±0.39	14.04±0.86	13.40±2.51
67	TVu-7838	2.62±0.01	0.80±0.02	9.55±1.74	12.62±1.36	9.60±1.95
68	TVu-7846	2.67±0.02	0.81±0.02	6.47±0.95	14.32±2.62	12.60±2.61
69	TVu-7848	2.95±0.00	0.74±0.01	6.22±1.07	14.30±0.82	11.40±2.30
70	TVu-7853	2.83±0.02	0.66±0.02	6.99±0.58	18.16±1.08	14.80±2.39
71	TVu-7870	3.32±0.03	0.85±0.00	11.65±1.92	21.44±1.49	17.40±3.05
72	TVu-7898	3.37±0.02	0.73±0.01	5.69±1.42	17.00±1.27	14.80±2.68
73	TVu-7920	2.63±0.04	0.88±0.03	6.53±1.19	18.90±1.52	16.60±2.79
74	TVu-7962	3.09±0.02	0.79±0.01	2.95±0.98	12.98±2.84	12.20±2.28
75	TVu-7983	2.92±0.03	0.79±0.04	4.12±0.41	12.30±1.14	9.60±1.52
76	TVu-7995	3.10±0.03	0.89±0.02	10.77±1.08	14.34±1.05	10.80±1.92
77	TVu-8042	3.45±0.05	0.70±0.03	6.14±1.22	12.92±1.18	10.40±2.70
78	TVu-8164	3.31±0.02	0.93±0.02	5.46±1.44	15.28±1.37	11.20±2.17
79	TVu-8387	2.93±0.04	0.83±0.02	11.52±0.978	16.62±1.54	12.80±2.39
80	TVu-8541	3.48±0.03	0.79±0.02	8.82±1.33	18.74±0.69	16.00±1.87
81	TVu-8546	3.38±0.04	0.83±0.01	2.23±0.25	15.66±1.03	11.60±2.07
82	TVu-8580	2.95±0.01	0.90±0.01	9.22±1.65	16.94±0.26	14.40±2.70
83	TVu-8586	3.20±0.03	0.84±0.03	7.01±1.42	18.42±1.71	16.00±2.83
84	TVu-9036	2.95±0.03	0.81±0.03	11.78±2.00	16.76±0.90	12.60±1.82
85	TVu-9167	2.90±0.02	0.78±0.03	6.62±1.47	13.90±1.06	10.20±1.64
86	TVu-9176	3.40±0.03	0.89±0.03	2.29±0.37	22.08±0.63	19.00±1.41
87	TVu-9185	3.43±0.03	0.97±0.03	6.50±1.66	13.26±0.51	15.20±1.64
88	TVu-9769	2.89±0.01	0.90±0.03	11.45±1.27	19.40±1.58	15.80±2.77
89	TVu-9772	3.15±0.03	0.90±0.04	7.56±0.91	14.62±1.16	12.80±3.27
90	TVu-9773	2.92±0.03	0.77±0.01	9.97±0.81	18.12±1.58	13.00±2.83
91	TVu-9774	3.12±0.02	0.70±0.03	8.23±1.78	18.46±2.04	13.00±3.00
92	TVu-9776	3.15±0.04	0.81±0.01	6.08±1.22	16.78±1.64	11.80±2.28
93	TVu-9779	3.18±0.01	0.81±0.03	8.89±1.43	17.52±1.16	17.80±0.84
94	TVu-9780	3.06±0.07	0.81±0.04	5.10±1.19	16.64±0.50	14.80±1.30
95	TVu-9784	2.98±0.02	0.95±0.02	7.59±1.43	13.52±1.85	12.40±1.14
96	TVu-9787	3.32±0.04	0.83±0.01	5.26±0.93	15.54±0.68	11.80±1.30
97	TVu-9788	2.99±0.01	0.79±0.01	3.63±0.69	14.26±1.37	13.20±2.95
98	TVu-9790	3.10±0.01	0.76±0.00	6.75±1.42	15.74±0.59	16.60±1.52

99	TVu-10112	2.99±0.01	0.83±0.02	6.25±1.06	15.74±1.22	14.60±2.70
Mean		3.10±0.23	0.78±0.08	6.96±2.97	16.01±2.84	13.29±3.16
P _{0.05}		< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
LSD _{0.05}		0.15	0.07	4.00	3.897	5.66
CV		1.38	2.45	16.06	8.87	15.51
n		3	3	3	10	10

N/B:SWPP = Seed Weight per Plant, PL = Pod Length, SNPP = Seed Number per Pod, LSD = Minimum Significant difference among mean values determined by Tukey's Test and CV = Coefficient of Variation.

Table 2. Pearson Correlation Coefficients among Phytic acid, Oxalic acid and Grain Yield Indices in Cowpea.

	Phytate	Oxalate	SWPP	PL	SNPP
Phytate	1.000	-0.077 (0.187)	0.026 (0.658)	-0.054 (0.358)	-0.095 (0.116)
Oxalate		1.000	0.018 (0.756)	0.012 (0.833)	0.072 (0.216)
SWPP			1.000	-0.020 (0.732)	0.015 (0.797)
PL				1.000	0.487* (<0.0001)
SNPP					1.000

N/B:* significant correlation. In parenthesis beneath the coefficients of correlation values are p-values, which indicate the level of significance of the correlation. Correlation is significant when p-value is < 0.05. SWPP = Seed Weight per Plant, PL = Pod Length and SNPP = Seed Number per Pod.

DISCUSSION

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L) Walp) is one of the most important food legume crops widely grown in semi-arid tropics as an inexpensive source of protein in both human diet and animal feed (Maheet *et al.*, 1994). However, the presence of antinutritional factors commonly found in legumes is a major factor limiting the wider food use of this essential tropical plant (Liener, 1980; Oke, 1969). For instance, phytic acid and Oxalic acid reduce mineral bioavailability that leads to various mineral deficiency diseases e.g. anaemia (Gluthrie and picciano, 1996), or form deleterious complexes with metal ions e.g. calcium-oxalate that leads to renal damage (Oke, 1969; Shukkuret *et al.*, 2006).

In this study, the variability of phytic and oxalic acid among the vast number of cowpea varieties grown in Nigeria was investigated to provide a guide for choice of cowpea lines based on phytate and oxalate contents. The relationships among the levels of these antinutrients and grain yield were also investigated to know if a choice of high grain yielding cultivar would mean choosing cowpea lines that are high in the antinutrients.

The result revealed significant variations in the antinutrients among the cultivars. The values ranged from 2.58 – 3.87 mg/g for phytate and 0.58 - 0.97 mg/g for oxalate with mean values of 3.10 and 0.78 mg/g respectively. These values for phytic acid compare well with 280 – 331 mg/100g (2.80-3.31 mg/g) reported for ten cowpea cultivars by Ologhobo and Fetuga (1983), but much lower than 5100-1027 mg/100g reported for thirteen cowpea lines by Farinu, G.O. and Ingraio, G. (1991). The values are also higher than 238.26mg/100g reported for afang (*Gnetum africanum*) seeds by Ekpo (2007), which the author noted are higher than tolerable limit permissible for children. Our results shows that cowpea seeds are high in phytic acid and should always be adequately processed to avoid phytate-related health risks especially among individuals who depend largely on cowpea for protein.

The values for oxalic acid are about 2.68 times lower than 209 mg/100g reported for afang seeds by Ekpo (2007). Thus, oxalate related problems are not likely to occur in healthy persons, except among individuals that consume large amounts on a long-term continuing basis and individuals with especial vulnerability to oxalates such as those with kidney disorders, gout and rheumatoid arthritis. Fortunately, most processing methods significantly reduce the antinutrients or totally eliminate some of them (Udensiet *et al.*, 2005 and 2007; Philips, 1993).

The result showed that cowpea contains more phytic acid than oxalic acid. The mean phytic acid obtained in this study was about four times higher than that of oxalic acid. This agrees with an earlier report by Weaver *et al.*, (1993). Finally, we found no significant correlation between phytic acid or oxalic acid and grain yield. So, grain yield has no influence on the seed content of any of these antinutritional factors in cowpea.

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